

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	CTU4H35A
Principle Investigator	Gerhard Gröbner
Structure/Description	Deuterated yeast polar lipid extract from Pichia Pastoris GS115 HSA: Phosphatidylcholine 66,0% Phosphatidylethanolamine 14,8% Phosphatidylinositol 7,1% Phosphatidylserine 6,7% Cardiolipin 3,5% Phosphatidylglycerol 1,6% Cells grown at 30°C and lipids extracted/analysed as described in: A. de Ghellinck et al., Production and Analysis of Perdeuterated Lipids from Pichia pastoris Cells, PLoS One, 9 (2014) 9.
Code	<i>dPichia Aug 2019 dpol 1-2</i>
Producer	Hanna Wacklin-Knecht/Fatima Plieva
Mass	53.5mg (dPichia Aug 2019 1-2)
% Deuteration	>99%
Analyses	<input type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other <u>_GC-FID_</u>

The lipids have changeable protons in the polar headgroups and should be freeze-dried from a small amount of D₂O (1-2mL) if full deuteration is required for experiments.

Figure 1. 2D HPLC separation of phospholipid classes for GC analysis. 3 = PE, 4 = CL, 5 = PG, 6 = PC, 7 = PI, 8 = PS

Figure 2. Distribution of fatty acids in the separated TLC fractions 3–8 from GC-FID analysis of their fatty acid methyl esters (Fame) using GC-FID peak areas. Error bar represents STDEV after two 2D-TLC.

Figure 2. Relative fatty acid composition of total phospholipid extract from GC:FID analysis of their fatty acid methyl esters (Fame) using GC-FID peak areas.

Figure 3. Relative phospholipid class composition of total deuterated yeast phospholipid extracts calculated from GC-FID data.

Table 1. A) Relative phospholipid class composition of total deuterated and non-deuterated yeast phospholipid extracts calculated from GC-FID data. B) Relative composition of fatty acids of different phospholipids for MID 1-7 and deuterated d 1-2. Error represents STDEV after two 2D-TLC.

A)

Phospholipid:	PC	PE	PI	PS	CL	PG
	66,0±3,7	14,8±2,0	7,1±0,2	6,7±0,4	3,5±0,3	1,6±0,0

d-Phospholipid:	PC	PE	PI	PS	CL	PG
dC14:0	0,3±0,0	-	-	-	-	-
dC16:0	4,4±0,5	15,2±1,8	45,5±1,2	46,8±3,3	3,1±0,7	38,3±0,1
dC16:1	2,4±0,1	1,0±0,2	1,2±0,1	-	-	-
dC17:0	0,3±0,0	-	0,1±0,0	1,5±0,2	-	-
dC17:1	1,1±0,1	0,1±0,0	-	-	-	-
dC18:0	4,5±0,2	5,3±0,2	11,1±0,4	8,2±0,2	2,1±0,3	-
dC18:1	69,5±1,5	52,3±5,4	38,0±4,1	32,9±4,8	44,0±3,6	27,4±1,7
dC18:2	15,0±0,3	23,5±0,4	4,8±0,8	2,5±0,1	30,7±1,0	4,9±0,8
dC18:3	1,0±0,0	0,3±0,1	-	-	1,5±0,6	0,2±0,1